

Unaccusatives in Slovenian Impersonals

Handout – SinFonIJA 16

Jakob Lenardič

`jakob.lenardic@inz.si`

Introduction

Aim: to account for the contrast in acceptability in the Slovenian pair in (1).

- (1) a. *Včeraj se je umrlo v bolnici. [Perfective unaccusative]
yesterday REFL is died.PFV.N in hospital
Intended: “Yesterday, some people died.”
- b. V vojni se je umiralo. [Imperfective unaccusative]
in war REFL is died.IPFV.N
“People died in the war.”

The previous – i.e., aspectual – approach:

- The contrast is due to an aspectual restriction on unaccusatives in impersonal constructions (e.g., Ruda 2014).
- Perfective verbs project an inner aspectual phrase, whose telicity feature needs to be checked by the internal argument (Borer 2005; van Hout 2004).
- The sole argument in (1) is structurally deficient (e.g., it lacks ϕ -features; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003), so it cannot check the telicity feature.

My proposal: (1b) is acceptable due to genericity rather than imperfectivity.

Argumenthood in Slovenian impersonals

Syntactic Anaphors (see also Fehrmann et al. 2010; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003; Szucsich 2008)

- (2) a. Bralo se je (**svojo**) knjigo. [Impersonal transitive]
read.N REFL is own.ACC.F book.ACC.F
“Some people were reading (their own) book.”
- b. Brala se je (***svoja**) knjiga. [Personal transitive]
read.F REFL is own.NOM.F book.NOM.F
“Some people were reading (*their own/the) book.”
- c. Umiralo se je za (**svoje**) ideale. [Impersonal unaccusative]
died.IPFV.N REFL is for own ideals
“People died for their own ideals.”

By-Phrases (see also Fehrmann et al. 2010; Lavine 2005; Ruda 2014)

- (3) a. Knjigo se je bralo (***s strani otrok**). [Impersonal transitive]
book.ACC.F REFL is read.N on part children.GEN
“The book was being read (*by children).”
- b. Knjiga se je brala (**s strani otrok**). [Personal transitive]
book.NOM.F REFL is read.F on part children.GEN
“The book was being read (by children).”
- c. Umiralo se je (***s strani vojakov**). [Impersonal unaccusatives]
died.N REFL is on part soldiers.GEN
“People were dying.”

Cross-Linguistic Comparison

- (4) a. (**Swoich**) przyjaciół tak się nie traktuje. [Polish]
own.GEN friends.GEN so REFL NEG treat.3SG
“One does not treat one’s friends like that.”
(Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003, p. 106)
- b. Je się maliny (***przez Marysię**).
eat.PRES.3SG.N REFL raspberries.ACC by Marysia
“Raspberries are eaten (*by Marysia).”
(Krzek 2014, p. 135)

- (5) a. Sluxalo-sja (*svoji) bat'kiv.
obey.PAST.SG.N-REFL own.ACC parents.ACC
 "People obeyed (*their own) parents."
 (Fehrmann et al. 2010, p. 206)
- b. (Matir"ju) myjet'sja dytnu
mother.INS wash.3SG.REFL child.ACC
 "The child is being washed (by the mother)."
 (Fehrmann et al. 2010, p. 206)

[Ukrainian]

In sum, Slovenian impersonals are like those in Polish but not Ukrainian in having a syntactically realised argument (external in transitives/unergatives and internal in unaccusatives).

The Unaccusativity Data

The Basic Questions:

1. Are unaccusatives actually licit in impersonals, with verb forms like *umrlo* (1a) being exceptionally unacceptable? Ruda (2014, p. 210): "an episodic event of dying cannot informatively be predicated of an unspecific undergoer."
2. Is there a perfectivity restriction on the use of unaccusatives with impersonal arguments (Borer 2005; van Hout 2004)?

Corpus Investigation

- **metaFida 1.0** (Erjavec 2023) – a metacorpora of existing Slovenian corpora; 4.7 billion words; diverse genres/registers.
- **Goal:** to check whether unaccusatives are attested in Slovenian impersonals in corpus data.
- **Verbs investigated:** the following 51 unaccusatives, both in their perfective and imperfective forms:

- (6) Slovenian unaccusatives (Ilc and Marvin 2016, pp. 149–150)
dozoreti "become ripe", *izginiti* "disappear", *izgoreti* "burn out", *izkrvaveti* "bleed out", *izpareti* "evaporate", *izzveneti* "cease to sound, die out", *obstati* "stop", *odleteti* "come off", *odpasti* "fall off", *odrasti* "grow up", *odreveneti* "stiffen", *odteči* "flow off", *oslabeti* "become weak", *ostati* "be left over", *otrdeti* "harden", *oveneti* "wither", *ozeleneti* "become green", *oživeti* "come to life", *pasti* "fall", *pobegniti* "flee", *pobledeti* "become pale", *počrneti* "become black", *porasti* "become overgrown with", *pordečeti* "become red", *porjaveti* "become brown", *porumeneti* "become yellow", *potemneti* "become dark", *posuroveti* "become brutal", *potoniti* "sink", *preživeti* "survive", *prileteti* "land", *prisesti* "sit down next to someone", *prispeti* "arrive", *priti* "arrive", *pristati* "land", *priteči* "flow from/arrive running", *razpasti* "fall apart", *umolkniti* "become silent", *umreti* "die", *uspeti* "succeed", *uveneti* "wither", *vstati* "rise", *vzkliti* "sprout", *zapasti* "expire", *zardeti* "blush", *zarjaveti* "rust", *zavreti* "boil", *zboleti* "get sick", *zginiti* "rot", *zmrzniti* "freeze", *znoreti* "become insane", *zrasti* "grow"

- **Finding 1:** All attested imperfectives consistently describe generic eventualities, as in (7); Interestingly, the imperfective unaccusative *umirati* "to die" is overrepresented in the corpus data.

- (7) Tako se je umiralo v Sloveniji v ofenzivah med 2. svetovno vojno.
thus REFL is died.IPFV.N in Slovenia in offensives during 2nd World War
 "People used to die this way in offensives during the Second World War in Slovenia."
 (*Gigafida 2.0*, Krek et al. 2019)

- **Finding 2:** Most of the 51 perfective forms are unattested (in past tense constructions), except for 6 verbs: *prispeti* "arrive", *preživeti* "survive", *priteči* "arrive running", *priti* "arrive", *pristati* "land".

- (8) Ko se je prispelo do gradbišča, so že čakali delavci Darsa.
when REFL is arrived.PFV.N to construction-site AUX.3PL already waited workers.NOM Dars.GEN
 "When some people arrived at the construction site, workers from Dars were already waiting."
 (*Kas-Dipl*, Erjavec et al. 2019)

- **Empirical gap:** Imperfectives with non-generic meanings (see also Lavine 2005).
- Constructed examples where generic event interpretation is blocked/unavailable are ungrammatical (9):

- (9) a. *Vstopili smo v bolniško sobo, v kateri se je v tistem trenutku umiralo.
entered AUX.1PL in hospital room in which REFL is in that moment died.IPFV.N
 Intended: "We had entered a hospital room in which some people were dying."
- b. *Včeraj se je s te zabave postopoma izginjalo.
yesterday REFL is from this party slowly disappeared.IPFV
 Intended: "Someone or some people were slowly disappearing from this party."
- c. *Včeraj se je krvavelo.
yesterday REFL is bled.IPFV.N
 Intended: "Someone or some people were bleeding yesterday."

- d. *Včeraj se je za te lapsuze gorelo.
yesterday REFL is for these lapsuses burnt.IPFV.N
 Intended: “Someone was being burned yesterday for these mistakes.”

Theoretical implications: The Aspectual Account (Borer 2005; van Hout 2004) does not predict the ungrammaticality of the non-generic imperfectives (9) or the grammaticality of certain perfectives (8).

The Analysis – Preliminaries

The Reflexive as a Voice Head

- The structure of VoiceP in Slovenian reflexive impersonals is as in (10):

- Syntactically, *se* is an active Voice head, so it requires a filled Spec (Bruening 2013; Schäfer 2017; Wood 2015). (C-selectional [S: X, S: Y] notation by Bruening 2013, 2021 instead of a [+D] feature, as in Legate et al. 2020; Schäfer 2017; Wood 2015.)
- Semantically, *se* expands VP with the Initiator relation (Kratzer 1996):

$$(11) \quad \llbracket se \rrbracket^g = \lambda f_{(s,t)} \lambda x \lambda e [\text{Initiator}(e, x) \wedge f(e)]$$

- A structure like (10) predicts the impersonal construction’s incompatibility with passivised (12a) and copular (12b) verbs – i.e., distinct impersonal Voice (Lavine 2017; Ruda 2014).

- (12) a. *Bilo se je poklicano (od župana). [Passivisation]
be.PAST.N REFL is call.PASS.N by mayor
 Intended: “Someone was called (by the mayor).”
- b. *Ko se je bilo mlad... [Copula]
when REFL is been young
 “When one was young...”
 (Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003, p. 112)

The Impersonal Pronoun

- Contra Schäfer (2017), *se* is not a structurally case-marked argument NP. Evidence: coexistence of *se* with NOM and ACC marked NPs in colloquial Slovenian.

- (13) a. Mi (ga) pijemo. [Colloquial Slovenian]
we it.ACC drink.IPFV.1PL
 “We’re drinking.”
- b. Lucija se (ga) je napila.
Lucija.NOM REFL it.ACC is drunk.PFV.F
 “Lucija got drunk.”

- The impersonal argument is *pro_IMP*; no ϕ -features (Ackema and Neeleman 2018; Fenger 2018; Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003), so default 3SG neuter agreement.
- Semantically, a (neo-Davidsonian) existential quantifier over people:

$$(14) \quad \llbracket pro_{IMP} \rrbracket^g = \lambda f_{(e,st)} \lambda e \exists x [\text{person}(x) \wedge f(e, x)]$$

- Rivero and Milojević Sheppard (2003) provide several pieces of evidence as to *pro_IMP*’s inherent quantificational status; e.g. no covariance:

- (15) Če se teorijo razloži slabo, se je navadno ne razume dobro.
if REFL theory.ACC explain.3SG badly REFL it.GEN normally NEG understand.3SG well
 “If one_i explains this theory badly, then one_j usually won’t understand it.”

- (21) a. Voda, **pritekla** iz izvira, je mrzla.
water.F arrived.F from spring is cold
 “The water that has flown from the spring is cold.”
- b. * Fant, **pritekkel** iz šole, je moj brat.
boy.M arrived.M from school is my brother.
 Intended: “The boy who has arrived running from school is my brother.”
 (Ilic and Marvin 2016, p. 150)

Generic Unaccusatives

- How to account for the contrast in (22)?

- (22) a. * Včeraj se je umrlo v bolnici. [Episodic]
yesterday REFL is died.PFV in hospital.
 Intended: “Yesterday, some people died in the hospital.”
- b. Še dandanes se umre od gripe. [Generic]
even nowadays REFL die.PFV from plague
 “People even nowadays die from the plague.”

- **Informal proposal:** this is an instance of “generic rescue” (Härtl 2012), as in:

- (23) a. * Yesterday, the tiger killed. [Episodic]
 b. * A large fire destroyed on Monday.
 c. * Yesterday, the book read.
- (24) a. The tiger kills to survive. [Generic]
 b. A large fire always destroys.
 c. The book reads easily.
 (Härtl 2012, pp. 103, 115)

- **Formal proposal:** allosemy (Marantz 2013; Schäfer 2017) of *se*:

- (25) a. If c-commanded by GN:
 $[[se]]^g = \lambda f \lambda e [f(e)]$
- b. Otherwise:
 $[[se]]^g = \lambda f \lambda x \lambda e [\text{Initiator}(e, x) \wedge f(e)]$
- (26) Syntax/semantics of grammatical Aspect (Ramchand 2008a):

- b. $[[GN]]^g = \lambda f_{(s,t)} \lambda g_{(s,t)} \lambda t \text{GNe} [[f(e) \rightarrow g(e)] \wedge t \in \tau(e)]$

- Allosemy of Voice independently needed elsewhere, e.g. difference between long and short passives (Bruening 2013; Schäfer 2017):

- (27) a. If c-commanded by Agentive PP:
 $[[\text{Voice}_{\text{PASS}}]]^g = \lambda f \lambda x \lambda e [\text{Initiator}(e, x) \wedge f(e)]$
- b. Otherwise:
 $[[\text{Voice}_{\text{PASS}}]]^g = \lambda f \lambda e \exists x [\text{Initiator}(e, x) \wedge f(e)]$

- VoiceP of (22b) is then as follows:

- (28) a.
-
- ```

graph TD
 VoiceP --> NP
 VoiceP --> VoicePrime[Voice']
 NP --> T1["△"]
 T1 --- proIMP["proIMP"]
 VoicePrime --> Voice
 VoicePrime --> VP
 Voice --> lambda["λ f λ e [f(e)"]
 lambda --- se["se"]
 VP --> lambda2["λ e ∃ x [person(x) ∧ die(e, x)]"]
 VP --> T2["△"]
 T2 --- umre["umre"]
 T2 --- proIMP2["proIMP"]

```

b. In (28a):  $[[VP]]^g = [[Voice']]^g = [[VoiceP]]^g$

- Allosemy constrained by the Monotonicity Condition (Koontz-Garboden 2009), so it does not apply to e.g. transitives.

## Summary and Cross-Linguistic Comparison

- In summary:
  1. The inadmissibility of episodic unaccusatives has the same cause as the inadmissibility of passivised predicates – that is, *se* as Voice.
  2. Impersonal unaccusatives are acceptable in predictable configurations (Agentivity or Genericity).
- Point 1 predicts that if an impersonal admits passivised predicates, then it should also admit unaccusatives:

- (29) a. Bywa się karanym przez przyjaciół. [Polish passivised impersonal *się*-construction]  
*be.3SG REFL punished by friends*  
“From time to time people are punished by friends.”  
(Rivero and Milojević Sheppard 2003, p. 112)
- b. Umarło się w czasie swojego ślubu. [Polish episodic *się*-unaccusative]  
*died.N REFL in time own.GEN wedding.*  
“Some people died at their own wedding.”  
(Online)
- (30) a. \*Bulo pokarano-sja (druzjamy). [Ukrainian passivised *sja*-construction ]  
*be.PAST.N punish.PASS.IMP-REFL friends.INS*  
Intended: “People were punished (by friends).”  
(Anna Kryvenko, p.c.)
- b. \*Včora vmerlo-sja. [Ukrainian episodic *sja*-unaccusative]  
*yesterday died.PFV.N-REFL*  
Intended: “Yesterday, someone or some people died.”  
(Anna Kryvenko, p.c.)

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